

**Opportunities and Challenges of Online Education:
An Interpretive Inquiry of Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta District**

A Mini Research

Submitted to

The External Examiner

The Research Management Cell

Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta

Submitted by

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February, 2021

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Tribhuvan University

धनकुटा बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, धनकुटा
DHANKUTA MULTIPLE CAMPUS, DHANKUTA

(प्रशासन शाखा)

पत्र संख्या: ०६६/०६८
चलानी नम्बर: १४३

क्याम्पस प्रमुखको कार्यालय

सम्मौता पत्र

धनकुटा बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, धनकुटाको अनुसन्धान व्यवस्थापन एकाइ द्वारा २०७७ सालमा सञ्चालन गरिने लघु अनुसन्धान परियोजना प्रयोजनका लागि तपाईं उपप्रा. श्री अम्बिकाप्रसाद पौडेलले अनुसन्धान व्यवस्थापन एकाइ, धनकुटा बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, धनकुटामा प्रस्तुत गर्नुभएको **Challenges and Possibilities of Online Education : An Interpretive Inquiry of Higher Education Institutions in Dhankuta** शीर्षकको लघु अनुसन्धान प्रस्ताव मूल्याङ्कन समितिद्वारा अनुसन्धानका लागि उपयुक्त ठहर्नाई सिफारिस गरेको हुँदा तपसिलका सर्तहरूका अधीनमा रहने गरी अनुसन्धान गर्न धनकुटा बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, धनकुटा र तपाईं उपप्रा. श्री अम्बिकाप्रसाद पौडेल विच यो करार सम्मौता गरिएको छ।

तपसिल

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- ६) अनुसन्धान कार्य सम्पन्न गर्ने क्याम्पसबाट जम्मा २ किस्तामा रु २०००० अक्षरेपी बीस हजार मात्र (करसहित) उपलब्ध गराइनेछ।
- ७) अनुसन्धानको प्रस्ताव मूल्याङ्कन तथा मौखिक परीक्षा बापत लाग्ने खर्च स्वयम् अनुसन्धाताले पाउने रकमबाट कट्टा गरिनेछ।

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क्याम्पस प्रमुख

मिति : २०७७/७/२४

Evaluation and Approval

This mini research report entitled **Opportunities and Challenges of Online Education: An Interpretive Inquiry of Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta District** prepared and presented by Ambika Prasad Poudel, a lecturer of English education; and carried out from 9th November, 2020 to 7th February, 2021, on behalf of Research Management Cell (RMC), Dhankuta Multiple Campus, has been evaluated and approved by following evaluation and approval committee.

MXX

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Acknowledgements

I feel myself extremely fortunate for having this opportunity to carry out this research on the important and more relevant issues– Opportunities and Challenges of Online Education in Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta district. I am indebted to all my gurus and all the scholars for their inspiration and invaluable ideas, which have a great contribution to complete this research work.

I express my gratefulness to the campus chief of Dhankuta Multiple Campus for providing me with this opportunity to conduct a research. Likewise, I am grateful to Research Management Cell, Dhankuta M. Campus for allowing me to carry out this mini research on the issues I am interested.

I am deeply grateful to all the chiefs/heads of the Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta district for agreeing to collect information relevant to the study. In the same way, I am thankful to all them for their kind support by giving information and ideas related to online education, and sharing their experiences of online activities as the participants. All those experiences and information have been really significant to make this research work complete and successful. Likewise, my thanks go to the students who took part in the online discussion, and shared their experiences and ideas.

My special thank goes to Mrs Shashikala Sharma, my life partner, who took all the responsibilities of the household works at home, and provided me an environment for reading, thinking and writing. I also thank Asmi, Asim, and Aayush, my kids, for creating a peaceful atmosphere while working.

Declaration

I hereby declare that this mini research entitled **Opportunities and Challenges of Online Education: An Interpretive Inquiry of Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta District** is my own and original research work, and it will become a part of permanent collection of Research Management Cell, Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta.

I understand that my signature below authorities release of my research work to any readers upon request.

.....

Ambika Prasad Poudel
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Abstract

This study entitled **Opportunities and Challenges of Online Education: An Interpretive Inquiry of Higher Educational Institutions in Dhankuta District** was a wonderful experience for me of carrying out a research work in one of the more relevant issues of present world, i. e., “Online Education”. The main objective of this research was to explore the opportunities and challenges of online education in the higher educational institutions in Dhankuta district. The study was also an attempt to study the current status of online education infrastructures, and the possible ways for the betterment in the existing situations of online education in those institutions.

This study was guided by constructivist research paradigm that stresses subjectivity and multiple realities. It adopted qualitative approach of research to study the social phenomena ‘the opportunities and challenges of online education and its practice in the higher educational institutions (HEIs) in Dhankuta district, Nepal. Altogether seven chiefs/heads from those HEIs were selected as the informants using purposive sampling methods, and a mail questionnaire was used as the research tool to understand their experiences and the online activities in those HEIs. Likewise, nine students studying master level were selected using stratified random sampling methods to collect the students’ experiences of online education. A virtual meeting was organized in Microsoft Teams to conduct a focus group discussion among the students using a FGD questionnaire. The information collected were analyzed using thematic analysis methods. The study found that the teachers and students in the HEIs were able to take some advantages of online education that it was useful for them for collecting more learning resources, for making interactions and discussions more frequent, and working in more collaborative ways. It was also found that still some of the HEIs were not able to run online education due to the lack of basic infrastructures such as Internet and laptops in the institutions that online education requires. The finding was also that though all the HEIs had same types of the challenges of online education, the opportunities they could achieve varied a great deal from one institution to another depending on their management and development of the pre-requisites needed for online education. Particularly, ICT infrastructures in the institutions, training to the teachers, and

the students' access to online tools were the main causing factors that affected the benefits the HEIs could achieve from online education. Therefore, it is important to address the challenges caused by these factors at both government and local level to make overall improvement in the existing situation of online education in the HEIS in Dhankuta district.

Abbreviations

AIR	American Institute of Research
B Sc	Bachelor of Science
BBS	Bachelor of Business Studies
BL	Blended Learning
CAN	Computer Association Nepal
CD	Compact Disk
CoI	Community of Inquiry
CWTs	Collaborative Web Technologies
CWTs	collaborative web technologies
DOI	Diffusion of Innovation
DVD	Digital Versatile Disk
HEIs	Higher Educational Institutions
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
INGOs	International Non-Governmental Organizations
IT	Information Technology
M A	Master of Arts
M B S	Master of Business Studies
M Ed	Master of Education
MOE	Ministry of Education

MPICTE	Master Plan of Information Communication Technology in Education
NCREL	North Central Regional Education Laboratory
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NIRT	National Institute for Research and Training
NPC	National Planning Commission
OCL	Online Collaborative Learning
OE	Online Education
RAAT	Resources and Appropriation Theory
SSRP	School Sector Reform Plan
STFT	Society of Technology Friendly Teachers
TYIP	Three Year Interim Plan
TYP	Three-Year Plan
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The innovations and advancements in information and communication technology (ICT) has been the heart of broad transformation in education in this 21st century world. The power of technologies has caused a paradigm shift in education; and effective education without the use of such technologies is impossible to imagine (Larson, 2017). The integration of technologies in education has offered not only new opportunities for communication and collaboration, but also that they provide the learners with authentic tasks, and access to a wealth of learning resources. Moreover, ICTs have been the key enablers of world globalization as they facilitate flows of information, and promote social development by knowledge sharing and increasing participation (UNDP, 2001). As a result, technology-based education such as online education (OE) and e- education have been increasingly widespread as the new modalities of education in recent years.

The terms such as online education, e-education, and technology-based education are sometimes used interchangeably. However, Carliner (2004) opines that each of these terms have specific meaning and distinct characteristics. Among these, technology-based education has a broader meaning, it refers to learning through any medium other than face to face classroom by integrating any instructional technology into the learning environment. This includes the technologies such as computers, television, audiotape, videotape, and print. On the other hand, online learning, refers to all types of learning that takes place through computer. It is a type of distance education that makes use of a range of technologies such as email, audio and video conferencing apps, chat, and the worldwide web. To Carliner (2004), online teaching and learning can be of mainly two types: (i) Virtual classrooms, which are the advanced type of online education in which students and instructors are geographically separated, but they do their work at the same time, and (ii) Online courses, which are the structured learning experiences presented on a computer, in which the instructor and the learner are separated by time and geography.

On the contrary, e-education or e-learning is a subset of online learning though it is

often used to refer to online learning. E-learning is an activity of acquiring knowledge or skills through the instruction provided through the internet. It is an electronically supported learning that relies on the internet for interaction between or among the teachers and learners. Therefore, learning through CD and DVD are not the forms of e-learning, although they are forms of online learning.

The importance of online education has been gradually increasing in this information age of 21st century world. It is because the expansion of ICTs has made this world a global village and it has transformed the nature of learning and the skills to acquire, which cannot be accomplished through the traditional mode of teaching and learning. The 21st century learning, emphasizes digital literacy, inventive thinking, effective communication, and high productivity (NCREL and Metiri group, 2003). 21st Century skills are more than technological literacy, they include proficiency in critical thinking, problem solving, communication, and team work (Paige, 2009). Thus, 21st century skills are a blend of content knowledge, specific skills, expertise, and literacies necessary to succeed in work and life. According to Ledward and Hirata, (2011), to achieve success in today's world, an individual requires 'the ability to access, synthesize, and communicate information; to work collaboratively across differences to solve complex problems; and to create new knowledge through the innovative use of multiple technologies' (p 1). Online education, that makes use of ICTs and internet, has potentialities to create environment for achieving these 21st century skills.

The development of online education does not have a long history in Nepal, and it is still crawling on its knee. Though computer association Nepal (CAN) was established in 1992, and Internet was introduced in 1993, there was no any remarkable activities regarding online education until IT policy-2000 was announced (Shakya, 2007, p. 11). The IT policy 2000 aimed to implement ICT related plans and policies and to assist research and computer related tasks. Likewise, three Year Interim Plan (TYIP)2007-2009, School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP) 2009-2015, IT policy 2010, and Three-Year Plan (TYP) 2011-2013 also revised the plans and strategies to address the issues for the development of ICT and online education in the country. More activity-based strategies in online education can be found in MPICTE (2013-2017), which aimed at ICT infrastructure development,

production of online learning materials, and ICT integration for quality enhancement in education (MOE, 2013).

In spite of all these plans and policies, the development of ICT infrastructure, and their integration in online education is still less satisfactory (NPC, 2019). Wallet (2014) reported that only 6% primary schools and 24% secondary schools have electrical and telecommunication infrastructure in Nepal, and 72% of the computers in the educational institutions were used for pedagogical purposes. Among the schools, only 1% of the primary level institution, and 6% of the secondary level institutions were connected to the Internet. Likewise, UNESCO found that 30.3% schools provided network technology for file sharing among the teachers, 14.9% teachers had email account from school server, and 9.0% schools provided e-library (UNESCO, 2015). After a research study, NPC (2019) reported that Nepal has 31% digital literacy, 83% of the people have access to radio, 72% to TV, and 55.5% to broadband Internet. It can be understood from all these reports that both infrastructure development, and online education in Nepal are still at early stage.

Dhankuta, one of the beautiful districts in eastern Nepal, was the head quarter of the eastern development region till 2019, is still one of the centers of educational activities in the eastern region. It is so because the head office of Education Development Directorate of province no 1 is located here, and the educational programs such as M. Ed., M. A., M B. S. and different bachelor programs including B. Sc have been running at Dhankuta Multiple Campus, one of the renown constituent campuses of Tribhuvan university. Moreover, though Dhankuta is geographically one of the small districts, there are six other community campuses, and two private campuses running educational activities. Likewise, more than 90 secondary schools, and over 190 basic schools have been running school education activities in this district.

Online education activities are stepping ahead in Dhankuta district following and/or guided by the IT related plans and policies mentioned above. However, as nationwide status of online education is at early stage, the higher education institutions (HEIs) in Dhankuta too cannot be an exception of this. Online education was a compulsion in the country including Dhankuta district due to Corona pandemic spread over the world, which pushed the country into lockdown, and that compelled to close the face-to face class in the

educational institutions. Meantime, Tribhuvan University issued a guideline to all its constituent and affiliated campuses to run online education as the best alternative mode of education. With reference to this context, the research and investigation regarding the opportunities and challenges of online education in the HEIs situated in Dhankuta has been an interesting subject of study.

1.2 Statement of the Problems

Digital technologies used in online education are powerful pedagogical tools, and their use has a significant role in the transfiguration of the pedagogy of teaching and learning (Ludvigsen & Morch, 2010; Sutherland, et al., 2009). Angeli et al. (2015) view that a good combination of technology and pedagogy is very important to ensure that the learners are able to take advantages of technology inclusion for the opportunities of online learning. Moreover, though multimedia and/or ICTs have been perceived as effective tools, ICT integration has ‘a long way to go and attain to maturity’ (Liu, 2012, p. 2334). Therefore, research and investigation on integration and use of ICTs in education is becoming worthwhile day-by-day in order to achieve the full advantages of technologies.

Online education can offer efficient and convenient ways to achieve learning goals (Dumford & Miller, 2018). Particularly, the learners in higher education who have to run their further study and job together, prefer online and e-learning rather than face to face mode of education (Kennedy & Archambault 2012; Poudel, 2018). Therefore, there is a large number of such learners who are unable to join the face to face mode of teaching and learning in the educational institutions. Thus, because face-to- face mode of teaching and learning can not provide service to all the students; research studies and investigation related to online education are more essential.

As several research studies (such as Angeli et al. 2015; Davis, 2007; Ludvigsen & Morch, 2010) have concluded that ICTs are useful educational tools; the government of Nepal has considered the need of ICT integration for the improvement of quality of education recently. However, the integration of ICTs in education in the developing countries is rather slow; and particularly, ICT integration in online education in Nepal is at its initial stage. Therefore, it is essential to explore the opportunities and challenges in ICT

integration in online education based on the context of Nepalese educational institutions because the knowledge gained from research studies is very important for tailoring the teaching-learning activities to integrate technological resources.

Furthermore, there are several studies that have explored the issues such as the characteristics and types of online education, and techniques and technologies used in online education. However, most of the studies are based on the developed country context, and the research studies that are based on the context of developing countries like Nepal are quite a few. Moreover, no attention has been given to study about online education being based in the context of Dhankuta district. Therefore, it is essential and worthwhile to carry out research studies to highlight the opportunities and challenges of online education in Dhankuta district.

The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education Master Plan (2013–2017) stressed the extensive use of ICT in online education for expanding access to and enhancing the quality of education (MoE, 2013; NIRT & AIR, 2017, p 126) in Nepal. Moreover, after the spread of Corona Virus, which compelled to close face to face classroom teaching and learning, online education was only the mode of teaching and learning even for those who were regular students in the face to face mode. As a solution, Tribhuvan University issued a guideline, and it urged its constituent and affiliated colleges to run online education because the ongoing lockdown made it impossible to conduct physical classes. Therefore, it has been essential to conduct a research study investigating the opportunities and challenges of online education in higher educational institutions.

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the background and the statements of the problems mentioned earlier, I have raised following queries as the research questions of this study:

- What is the present status of online education in terms of infrastructure development and online education practice in the higher educational institutions (HEIs) in Dhankuta district?
- What are the opportunities and challenges of online education in the HEIs?

1.4 Objectives

To explore some relevant issues about online education in the institutions of higher education in the context of Dhankuta district is the general objective of this study. The specific objectives are:

- To describe the current status of online education in terms of infrastructure development and online education practice in higher education institutions in Dhankuta district?
- To explore the opportunities and challenges of online education in HEIs.
- To highlight the possible measures for the betterment in the existing situation of online education in the HEIs.

1.5 Rationale of the Study

Online education has been increasingly spreading in recent years and there is a large number of students who prefer online education rather than face-to-face teaching. Online education was an obligatory mode of education due to Corona pandemic and country lock down. The research study with an aim of exploring the opportunities and challenges, the status and practice of online education, and the possible measures for its improvement is essential to develop the insights of the teachers, students, educators, school supervisors, and education administrator about online education for making further strategies. Likewise, the study report on the opportunities and challenges of online education is also needed to all concerned authorities to use as guideline document while reviewing the implementations of prepared plans and making further strategies and policies about online education.

1.6 Delimitations

To study the current status of online infrastructures in the HEIs in Dhankuta district, the opportunities and challenges of OE, and the possible ways for the betterment of OE was the main aim of the study. This study has following delimitations:

- This study has adopted interpretivism research paradigm and qualitative research design.
- Only the mail questionnaire, and focus group discussion through virtual meeting have been used as the research methods.
- The study has included the chiefs/heads of only the TU affiliated community campuses (HEIs), and constituent campuses located in Dhankuta district as the informants for online mail questionnaire; and the students of master level only from TU affiliated campus representing education, humanities, and management faculties from the district.
- Only some aspects, i. e., status of the infrastructures needed for online education; and opportunities and challenges of online education have been the main concerns of the study.

1.7 Organization of the Study Report

In addition to the preliminary parts and the references and appendices, the main body of this study report has been organized into five chapters: (i) Introduction, (ii) Review of Related Literature, (iii) Methodology, (iv) Findings, and Analysis, and (v) Summary, Conclusion and Implications. The first chapter is introduction which has included the background of the study, statement of problem, rationale of the study, objectives of the study, research questions, and delimitations. Likewise, the second chapter has consisted of the review of related literature, implication of the literature review, the theoretical framework, and conceptual framework. In the same way, the third chapter has dealt with research paradigm, research design, tools and methods of data collection and data analysis, and ethical considerations. The fourth chapter has consisted of findings of the results and their analysis, and the fifth chapter has dealt with the main summary of the findings, conclusions drawn, and the implications of the study.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Review of Related Literature

Reviewing related literature is one of the main requisites of any academic research. A review of literature can help widen the knowledge and clarify the concept. It is also important to find out the research gap and form theoretical and conceptual framework for the study. A thematic literature review of the related literature of this study has been presented in the following sub heading.

2.1.1 Learning Theories and Online Education

A learning theory is a statement or an explanation of the learning processes. The query ‘how people learn, and where knowledge comes from and how people come to know’ have been an everlasting inquiry from centuries. As the solution, two opposing positions emerged in the philosophical arena– empiricism and rationalism (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). Empiricists claim that experience is the primary source of knowledge that is derived from sensory impressions. Rationalists on the other hand, view that knowledge is derived from the reasoning in the mind of the learners, and it is the result of active mental processing (p. 47). These two philosophical viewpoints generated two polarized positions as the theories of learning: (i) behaviorism or the behavioristic/empiricist theory and (ii) cognitivism or the cognitivist/rationalist theory. The theories and approaches such as constructivism, constructionism, information processing learning, multiple intelligences, online learning, blended learning, electronic literacy approach (ELA) have been emerged from these two polarized positions (Picciano, 2017).

Behaviorism, that is associated with Ivan Pavlov and J B Watson focuses on how people behave while learning. The behaviorists give emphasis on the study of stimulus and response arguing that mind and consciousness are unimportant in learning process (Picciano, 2017). On the other hand, cognitivism, that is associated with Gagne and Sweller, stresses that learning is a mental activity that requires internal coding and structuring by the learner (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). The cognitivists view that only shaping

and changing behavior is not possible way of learning, it is an active mental activity where information comes as an input, and it is processed to be output.

A number of theories that are appropriate for online education have been derived from the major learning theories discussed above. Constructionism, a theory propounded by Seymour Papert, considers learning as ‘building knowledge structures through progressive internalization of actions’. It argues that knowledge is constructed through conscious engagements of the learners in constructing meaningful products in technology integrated environments. (Papert, 1991). Likewise, connectivism, a theory of information flow, was proposed by G Siemens in 2004. It assumes that learning is a process of connecting specialized nodes or information sources, and this can be promoted with the help of ICTs.

The community of inquiry (CoI) model for online learning environment was developed by Garrison, Anderson & Archer (2000). It requires the presence of three distinct concepts ‘cognitive, social, and teaching’, and emphasizes on the interaction among the instructors and students using the tools such as discussion board, blogs, wikis and video conferencing (Picciano, 2017, p 173). Similarly, online collaborative learning (OCL) is a theory proposed by Linda Harasim in 2012. It stresses the significance of Internet to provide a good learning environment. It is “a new theory of learning that focuses on collaborative learning, knowledge building, and Internet use as a means to reshape formal, non-formal, and informal education” (Harasim, 2012, p. 81).

2.1.2 Opportunities created by ICTs in online education

ICT are supposed to be a backbone of online education. A research study in this light was carried out by Asli, Berrado, Sendide, and Darhmaoui (2012) in Morocco. The purpose of the research was to investigate how ICT-based education could improve motivation and performance of the students, and to demonstrate the effect of the ICT resources on the scholastic performances of the students. The findings were that in middle school, the performance of the experimental group was far better with 85% confidence level for all level students. The conclusion was that ICT-based education had positive impact in students’ performance, but the impact was not consistent in the schools with

different socio-economic conditions.

Trushell, Byrne, and Hassen (2013) did a study about students' use of ICTs (i. e., purposes of using virtual learning environment (VLE), and Internet), and students' engagement on lecturer impressing strategy and cheating behavior such as plagiarism. The result of the study disclosed that the younger students had greater tendency of being engaged in social internet activity such as maintaining blog, and leisure time activities like playing online games, and downloading film, and music. They had also greater tendency to be engaged in certain lecturer impressing behavior. The students were engaged relatively less frequently in downloading educational materials such as lecture notes and recommended readings. The study found that there were strong positive correlations between frequency of e-mail correspondence by VLE and Internet activities of looking for information about studies and looking for news and current affairs.

ICTs are very encouraging for the potentiality of collaboration that can raise the quality of learning. Repiso, Pablos, and Garcia (2014) carried out a study to explore the teachers' experience about the advantages and disadvantages of collaborative learning. They also aimed to discover the teachers' concept about the use of ICTs to support collaborative learning environment. The result indicated that ICTs have potential capacity for enhancing collaborative activities and also for developing relevant generic skills. Some of the advantages of collaborative learning were: (i) development of transversal learning skills, (ii) interaction among students, (iii) increasing students' attention and participation, (iv) increasing motivation and learning, (v) promoting personal satisfaction of students, (vi) improvement in teacher professional development.

Pima, J. M., Odetayo, M., Iqbal, R., and Sedoyeka, E. (2016) carried out a research about collaborative learning environment, and availability of collaborative web technologies (CWTs) . It was a case study of six higher education institutes (HEIs) in mixed methods approach. Pima et al (2016) argued that a good ICT infrastructure is an essential element for the use and adoption of CWT-enabled blended learning (BL). CWT-enabled BL, a popular instructional model in higher education, offers lots of benefits to learners and the lecturers such as: (i) effective communication between the students and the lecturers, (ii) student centered generation of new knowledge and engagement, and (iii)

appropriate mix of technologies and learning process. Their finding was that internet, power supply, computer literacy, wikis, blogs, social networking media, learning management information systems (LMIS) are some of the important ICT infrastructures that support CWT-enabled BL.

2.1.3 Challenges and barriers in online education

There are several books, journal articles, theses, and reports available related to the study of challenge and barriers in online education. Bjorn, Massen, Borgan, Oftebro & Kerseth (2007) made an empirical study on the use, updating, and integration of ICT in online education. They aimed at analyzing the important factors for the implementation of ICT in higher education and carried out a multiple case study of five higher educational institutions in Norway. The finding of the study disclosed that there were adequate economic resources and well-developed technological infrastructure and support in the higher education in Norway. However, the study recommended a better link among human and organizational issues that were not so successful.

As an attempt to explore about the integration of ICTs in teaching and learning activities, Wang (2014) carried out a research in Taiwan. The research questions in his study were: (i) what are the current practices of ICT by language teachers in higher education? and (ii) what emotions are involved in the integration of ICT into language courses? (p. 188). The study found that the teachers had positive attitude towards integrating ICTs, and most of them were happy in their utilization. The most common communication tools were power point presentation, and you tube. But it was found that they were unwilling to using them in their teaching and learning activities mainly because they didn't have adequate knowledge about the technologies, they found it difficult to maintain discipline, they had insufficient preparation time, and also that they didn't have idea about the value of some of the technological tools. The result showed that the teachers had some negative emotions like dispiritedness, anxiety, and insecurity.

Schrum and Levin (2013) carried out a study about promoting technology integration for professional development of the teachers. They conducted a multiple case study of the eight exemplary technology-using schools located in different cities in the

USA. The conclusions were drawn triangulating the data resources from interviews, observation, and document reviews. They concluded that for promoting technology integration to improve the students' engagement and achievement, teachers' effort, energy, and professional development are essential. Effective use of technology can only be assured if the teachers possess expertise of technological and pedagogical knowledge in teaching and learning.

Hutchison and Reinking (2011) conducted a research to explore the teachers' perception of ICT integration into literacy instruction. The result showed that the integration of the ICTS into literacy instruction was not so high primarily due to factors like pedagogical and content knowledge of the teachers, and due to the obstacles to be faced by them. The path analysis used suggested that the factors like pedagogical skills, competency, support, stance, and availability were major causing obstacles.

Hu and McGrath (2011) studied on the use of ICT in classroom teaching and self-access learning. They aimed at examining the attitude of the teachers, towards the use of ICTs, and practices and policies of ICT-related professional development in southern China. The finding of the study was that the teachers were positive towards the use of ICTs, and in ICT-related continuing professional development. However, the results showed that the inadequate support and training, insufficient pedagogical content knowledge and skills were the major obstacles.

With regard to the barriers of ICTs, Salehi and Salehi (2012) carried out a research to examine the teachers' perception of the barriers and challenges that prevent them to integrate ICTs. The conclusion of the study was drawn that the high school language teachers were familiar with ICTs and ICT usage. It was found that insufficient technical support to the teachers, and little access to Internet were the main barriers. It was also reported that the teachers faced shortage of class time, and time for their professional development to learn about ICT skills.

Umar and Jahil (2012) conducted a research to examine the students' level of ICT skills, and their barriers. The purpose of the research was also to study the difference in the ICT skills of male and female students, and urban and rural students. The study disclosed

that majority of the students were skillful ICT basic and communication skills. They were moderately skilled with Internet application for information skills but were poor in advanced level ICT skills like multimedia creation. In comparison the urban area students showed better skills at all four levels of ICT skills, and it is due to the digital divide. There was not a significant difference between male and female students regarding ICT skills. The two main barriers found in the study were concerned with administration, and ICT resources facilities.

Goketas, Gedik, and Byadas, (2013) have conducted a research investigating the perceived behaviors about the barriers experienced by the Turkish primary school teachers; and potential enablers to overcome such barriers. The results indicated that lack of infrastructures (hardware, and software), lack of in-service training, and lack of technical support were the main barriers of ICT integration. Similarly, financial support (allocation of budget), technical and pedagogical support, and designing appropriate course/instructional programme were reported as the perceived enablers.

This review of related literature gave an insight that many learning theories such as constructionism, connectivism, CoI, OCL are appropriate for online education. OE has possibilities of providing several opportunities such as motivation, accessing learning resources, and enhancing collaborative learning. Likewise, inadequate knowledge of technology and pedagogy, insufficient technical support, low capacity internet, and lack of financial support were some of the main barriers of online education.

2.2 Implications of Literature Review

Several research studies related to online education have been carried out such as Ertmer and Newby, (2013); Goketas, Gedik, and Byadas, (2013); Salehi and Salehi (2012); Trushell, Byrne, and Hassen (2013); Wang (2014); Picciano, (2017), and so on. The review of these research works has helped conceptualize the knowledge and ideas, and strengthened insights about the phenomenon. Likewise, the review has provided insightful knowledge to formulate theoretical and conceptual framework for the study. However, it has been found that most of the research works have been carried out in the foreign country context, outside Nepal. Such studies are not adequate enough to address and operate the

issues based on the realities of Nepalese educational context. Moreover, no attention has been paid to carry out the research related to online education being based in the context of Dhankuta District. This is the research gap that the review of related literature enlightened; and this study has been expected to fulfill this research gap.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by the Resources and appropriation theory (RAAT) of diffusion, acceptance, and adoption of technology as the theoretical framework. This theory, proposed by J.A.G.M. van Dijk in 2005, is based on the relational theory of digital divide, and is further expansion of diffusion of innovation (DOI). As online education is an innovation in teaching and learning that makes use of digital technologies, RAAT is appropriate for studying about it. Dijk discusses a relational theory of inequality in which she points out a need of the analytical explanation of digital divide that concerns with inequalities of computer and Internet access, and digital skills (van Dijk, 2013). She views that inequality is concerned with not only individualistic notion but is related to individuals and their characteristics such as level of income and education, employment, age, sex, and ethnicity. In this interpretation of inequality, the prime unit of analysis is not the individual, but the position of the individuals, or the categorical differences of individual such as white/black, male/female, employer/employee; and the firsts of these categories are the dominant for the adoption of technologies. The RAAT model proposed by van Dijk claims that the access and adoption of any new technology is the part of such characteristic differences. The four basic concepts of the theory (RAAT) are (van Dijk, 2013, p. 32):

- A number of personal and positional categorical inequalities in societies,
- The distribution of resources relevant to this type of inequality,
- A number of kinds of access to ICTs, and
- A number of fields of participation in society.

These four basic concepts are independent and also interlinked one another; and the following ones are the consequences of the previous ones. The first and the second concepts are the causes, and the last two are the potential consequences. Likewise, the last

two provide feedback to the earlier ones. The arguments among these concepts in the theory (van Dijk, 2013, p 33) are:

- Categorical inequalities in society produce an unequal distribution of resources,
- An unequal distribution of the resources causes unequal access to digital technologies,
- Unequal access to digital technologies also depends on the characteristics of these technologies,
- Unequal access to digital technologies brings about unequal participation in society,
- Unequal participations in society reinforces categorial inequalities and unequal distributions of resources.

In the relational theory of digital divide, Van Dijk (2013) discusses the inequalities in four types of access: motivation, physical access, digital skills, and different usage. Dijk explains that the adoption of new technology requires motivation to be developed in the users, and there can be inequality in motivation due to the factors such as lack of money, lack of skills, computer anxiety, and techno-phobia. When sufficient motivation is developed, the users should have physical access to technology such as computer, Internet, software, subscription etc. The differences in the physical access to technology is caused by the distribution of resources and several other factors such as income, age, sex, intelligence, personality, ability, and position of the users. Likewise, the users need to develop different types of technological skills such as medium related skills (operational skills, and formal skills, e.g., browsing, navigating), and content-related skills (information skills, communication skills, strategic skills, and content-creation skills), differences in which create inequalities. Similarly, inequalities are also created due to the diversity in usage: the types of application used and the time and frequency of the use of technologies of the users.

It is argued that the appropriation of technology in online or technology-based education is affected by the factors such as motivation, physical access to technologies and

materials, and digital skills for using them. However, it is also claimed that these factors do not automatically lead to appropriation of the technologies. In other words, ‘having sufficient motivation, physical access, and skills to applying digital media are necessary but not sufficient conditions of actual use of technologies’ (p. 43). Additionally, the appropriation can be measured by the time and frequency of usage, and the number of the diversity of applications, and their active and creative use. RAAT can be one of the useful theories to study various aspects of online education.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework, simply, is the researcher’s understanding to explore the research problem and related concepts or ideas. It is not just a string of the concepts, but it is a way to identifying the researcher’s research paradigm and research problem. According to Grant and Osanloo (2014), the conceptual framework ‘offers a logical structure of connected concepts that help provide a picture or visual display of how ideas in a study relate to one another within the theoretical framework’ (p. 17). It is the scheme of concepts,

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

variables, and method that the researcher operationalizes in order to achieve the set of objectives. Miles and Huberman (1994) view, a conceptual framework is a system of concepts, assumptions, and beliefs that support and guide the research plan that ‘lays out the key factors, constructs, or variables, and presumes relationships among them’ (p. 440).

This study aims at exploring the challenges and possibilities of online education in the higher education institutions in Dhankuta district with the theoretical lens of RAAT. The study will be based on constructivists' philosophy, and will be guided by qualitative research design. The Heads of the HEIs and students will be the informants, and mail questionnaire, and online interview will be used as the research tools to collect information which will be analyzed thematically. The diagram in Figure 1 reflects the conceptual framework of this study.

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Paradigm: Constructivism

Research paradigm refers to the philosophical worldview that guides the researcher while conducting a research or investigation. Among some well-known philosophical worldviews in the educational research (such as positivism, post-positivism, constructivism, feminism, pragmatism), the research paradigm this study will adopt is ‘constructivism’. Constructivism was stimulated as a result of the dissatisfaction with growing overemphasis of experimentation and quantitative methods that considers mathematics as ‘the queen of sciences’ (Guba & Lincoln, 1994, p. 105). The constructivists claim that knowledge is constructed socially, and that individuals seek understanding of the world in which they live or work (Creswell, 2014, p. 42). It is therefore, to constructivists, there are multiple realities, multiple meanings, and multiple interpretations. As constructivism will be the philosophical base, the axiological, ontological, epistemological, and methodological stands of constructivism will be the philosophical beliefs in this study too.

3.2 Research Design: Qualitative

Qualitative research design is derived from the qualitative research approach. Qualitative approach emphasizes the exploration of meaning and conclusion by means of the interpretation of the observation or experiences (Creswell, 2014). The principle behind the qualitative research design is that a research problem or an issue is better understood so as to make its sense by contrasting, comparing, replicating, or by classifying its data resources (Mertens, 2010). It is well-suited to generate new theories, to achieve deep understanding of particular phenomenon, or to give a detail narrative description of the issue. Based on the qualitative research design, the detail of the issues of this study, i., e., the challenges and possibilities of online education will be explored in this research study.

3.3 Study Site: Dhankuta District

The study site in this research work was the higher education institutions situated in Dhankuta district. Particularly, the TU constituent and TU affiliated community campuses located in Dhankuta district (see Appendix- C) were purposefully selected as the field of study.

3.4 Informants

The informants in this study were the seven chiefs/heads of the higher education institutions from the TU constituent and TU affiliated and community campuses in Dhankuta district, and they were given pseudonyms— C1, C2.....C7 for confidentiality in the research (Saunders, Kitzinger, & Kitzinger, 2015). They were requested to share their experiences and information about the issues of the study. Likewise, the students studying their master level in the TU affiliated campus were also the participants in this study. Three students from each M.Ed., M. A, and M. B. S. programs were selected using stratified random sampling methods to make the study free from biasness. The students were given pseudonyms— S1, S2.....S9 to make their information confidential as guided by research ethics (Saunders, Kitzinger, & Kitzinger, 2015). As there was only one campus that ran master level programs in the district, the students from all the rural/municipalities study there; and these students were expected to represent the students of the whole district.

3.5 Research Methods/Tools

The study was conducted in the time of lock down in the country caused by the pandemic of Corona virus in the world. Because it was almost impossible to use other than the online tools for the collection of data, mainly two types of research tools were used in this study to collect relevant information:(i) Mail questionnaire, and (ii) Focus Group Discussion through virtual meeting using Microsoft Team. The mail questionnaire was (see Appendix-A) used to collect the experiences and information about the challenges and possibilities of online education from the heads/chiefs of the selected campuses. Likewise, focus group discussion using FGD questionnaire (see Appendix-B) through virtual meeting in Microsoft Teams (Ms Teams link:

Team<https://teams.microsoft.com/l/team/19%3a6df5fae1d0744270bf2f71eda913b917%40thread.tacv2/conversations?groupId=671fbbc2-9961-4533-808c-bac9beb4d146&tenantId=457a287e-c649-4355-817e-30f728e578d8>) was used to obtain the experiences and information from the students. The meeting was held for one and half hour and it was recorded on the laptop computer. The mail questionnaire and the questions to be discussed in the virtual meeting were prepared carefully in such a way that they could help obtain required information from the informants.

3.6 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis methods were used to analyze and interpret the information collected. The information obtained through mail questionnaire was read and re-read, and the meeting recording was watched and listened to several times to understand the ideas and experiences collected. After that, themes were generated after segmenting, coding, and categorizing the information collected. Finally, the themes were analyzed and interpreted based on the facts and findings obtained.

3.7 Trustworthiness and Dependability

The terms such as trustworthiness, dependability, validity and reliability refer to the quality aspects of a research work. Trustworthiness in qualitative research is one of the key elements to an effectiveness of a research that maintains the quality like honesty, richness, in-depth, credibility, and accuracy. Dependability/Reliability is considered as the synonym of consistency of action or event over time. It is the quality of a research work that demonstrates systematic operations of the study.

To strengthen trustworthiness, strong attempt was made in this study by giving a clear and detail description of the methods and procedures. The researcher was more careful and honest for keeping accuracy of the information. Likewise, for maintaining dependability, interview protocol (see Appendix-A), and FGD protocol (see Appendix-B), were developed and used to make the study more systematic and comprehensive.

3.8 Ethical Consideration

Research ethics refer to the conduct of the investigator based on professional codes and values such as authorship and attribution of credit, taking permission from the institution and consent from the participants, respecting the participants' confidential, and so on. In this research work, I took permission from the Heads/chiefs to collect data, and consents was taken from the students to collect their experiences related to the topic. I was much careful not to shake the data and information collected in their analysis and interpretation. I carefully gave credit for ownership of the resources—books, articles, theses etc. All the informants were treated equally, and I was careful not to harm them and not to disclose their confidentiality.

CHAPTER IV: FINDING AND ANALYSIS

This chapter deals with the findings of the study obtained from the interviews with the Heads of the campuses and from FGDs with the students. The findings have been discussed based on the issues of the study; and their analysis and interpretation have been presented in the sub-headings to come.

4.1 General Impression and Attitude towards Online Education

Most of the informants, particularly, the chiefs of the higher education institutions in Dhankuta district were found to be positive towards online education. They opined that online education could help make teaching-learning any time anywhere possible. During the lockdown period, there was no any way for them except online mode of education. One of the informants, C5 shared:

We relied completely on online education during Corona lockdown period. I am positive with online education, it would be better to be implemented online education in almost all schools of Nepal; and it needs to be continued with adequate preparation to support both teachers and students where it is being practiced.

The informants opined that online education is more effective and less expensive than traditional education. Online education has been extremely essential in the changing world context. Informant C2 gave his opinion, “*Online education has been only the way that connects the teachers and students in the pandemic of corona virus. It is also very useful to the students who are unable to attend face to face classes.* Likewise, informant C6 viewed, “*Online education plays vital role but radical change is necessary in our education system and for approaching it to majority of students*”.

The opinions of the heads of the HEIs can be analyzed that they found online education useful and effective. However, they viewed that online education has been unable to be in approach to many of the students. It is because in the developing country Nepal, the internet, and electricity, and other online education tools were also not easily available to the students. Many of the students lack broadband internet and laptop essential for online education. Thus, though there are many challenges, online education is a useful mode of education.

The campus chiefs of the HEIs in Dhankuta district found their teachers who have access to and skills of using the online educational tools to have positive attitudes towards online education. Likewise, the students who had online learning tools showed positive behavior towards online education. The informant C5 wrote:

The teachers who are active, capable and trained in computer have positive attitude but others who feels teaching as job and not have such capacity or knowledge ignore and have negative attitude. The students who have access of it have positive attitude.

Informant C6 experienced that online education has brought both new challenges and new opportunities in context of Nepalese educational institutions. Thus we need to face the challenges to grab the opportunities. He opined:

Firstly there are few people to accept the new challenge in our country, however, necessity, importance, understanding, planning as well as time management for accepting the challenge makes everything possible. Same thing has happened in our institution. The teachers and students in our institution didn't think it possible at first, later, it was thought possible and it came to action.

OE is easier than traditional face-to face mode of teaching and learning. Informant C7 viewed:

The teachers felt the online education easier way than traditional methods as they can convey the messages/contents to the students without leaving their room. There are however, many dissatisfaction from the students as they need to face several problems such as irregular power supply, poor internet capacity, and problems of access to online learning tools.

Likewise, OE helped to collect different learning materials. OE has made content delivery easier. However, the students were not able to be clear about concepts in comparison to the traditional methods. Informant C1 shared:

Most of the teachers agreed that it is one of the better alternative mode of education. Most of the students gave their reaction that they could have many learning

resources, but could not clearly understand the concepts or contents while being involved in online education.

The students in the FGD opined that online education was useful for them. Most importantly, OE was more appropriate for those who could not be regular in the class due to their job or family responsibility. One of the informants, S5 said, *“I was irregular in the face to face class, but I have been taking the class regularly in this OE mode”*. It was also useful for those regular students in case they missed their classes. More importantly, online education developed their habit of collecting several relevant learning materials. They experienced that OE has helped them be more resourceful. They were able to make their interaction more frequent and were able to work more collaborative activities. Another informant, S3 shared:

I am positive with OE and it is very useful for me that has helped me become anytime learner. I have been able to collect the needed learning resources, and I can use them whatever time I like. And more importantly, I did not need to pay for those other than my Internet cost. S6 expressed, In OE, interaction is easier and more frequent. It has helped me to get rid of many of my confusions.

From the excerpts above it can be understood that the chiefs of the HEIs and most of their teachers had positive attitude towards OE. They had understood OE as one of the effective modes of education that would make the students all time learners. OE was good for them to collect and share learning resources. More importantly, OE was useful for interaction and discussion among the teachers and the students that could minimize the students' confusions. Many of the students were not used to participating OE. Therefore, OE could impress only a few of them it was because many of the students neither had OE tools such as internet, laptops, and Mobile phones; not do they had basic skills of OE.

4.2 Existing Status of Pre-Requisites of Online Education

The status of existing infrastructures was found to have been varied in different HEIs. Some of the institutions were quite poor in the management of online infrastructures, while some of them were relatively more satisfactory to manage the basic infrastructures of online education. The informant C5 wrote:

We have enough access of internet due to having 3 different Internet connectivity (NTC fiber -2 and Techminds-1) with Wi-Fi as well as cable in every class rooms. Smart TVs have been managed. Computer lab with 15 desktop computers, Projectors and Smart boards in some class rooms, 90% teachers having laptop and being familiar with on- line education, running online education. In the lockdown period, most of the students and teachers developed skills of online education.

C2 shared, *“In our institution, we have managed the basic infrastructures for online education such as the Internet, desktops and laptops. The teachers are quite interested and curious to develop the skills needed for online education”*. Likewise, another informant C4 wrote, *‘We have managed the basic infrastructures needed for online education. Our students, however, do not have proper access to online education tools’*. In the same line another informant C7 expressed, *“We have managed some of the infrastructures. Due to lack of budget we have not been able to fulfil our basic requirements. Moreover, not all teachers have developed the skills needed for online education”*. C6 mentioned:

The existing status of pre-requisites belonging online education is in continuous process for well- management. Approximately, 60% of its management has been possible. Too much expenditure for computers ‘purchase, training for teachers and high speed of internet management was the great challenge for our institution; however, we are near to achieve our goal.

OE in the HEIs had some basic infrastructures such as Internet, e-library, though they were not adequate. Many of the teachers had some basic skills of OE . Informant C1 put:

Internet facility is available, though its speed is rather low. There is one e-library and an ICT lab but is unable to provide service to all the students as their number is quite large. The teachers are not confident about online teaching. Some training programmes to the teachers were organized, though they are not adequate. Many of the students do not have access to ICT/online resources.

Management of infrastructure was one of the main factors of students' dissatisfaction of online education. Most of the students reported that online education was useful for them but they didn't have access to its prerequisites. One of the main problem was poor management of online infrastructures such as internet laptop and smartphones. One of the informants S3 shared, *"Internet speed is one of the main problem to us. The internet capacity is so poor that it takes long time for us to open MS team and zoom. Likewise S7 expressed, "Sometimes I do not see the contents shared by my teacher. The screen-sharing is so delayed that the teacher is explaining one thing while the screen is about another thing". S8 said, "The electricity is often interrupted and it takes long time to rejoin the class. I have missed lots of lessons due to power cut"*.

Lack of online learning devices/tools was another infrastructural problem to the students. S2 said, *"I used my mobile phone and it doesn't support some of the content shared by my teacher"*. Similarly S4 added, *"My laptop is old and it takes long time to open and it doesn't support many of the application"*.

It can be summarized that must of the HEIs have been able to manage some of the basic infrastructures needed for OE such as internet and computers. However, its management in some of the institution was too poor. Even in the institution where is has been managed, the internet speed, ICT lab and the number of computer or laptop was quite small and it was inadequate to the number of students. Many of the students did not have access to essential online learning tools. The students were interested but were disappointed due to lack of online learning tools and infrastructures.

4.3 Opportunities Created by Online Education in HEIs

Online education created several opportunities to the HEIs. Most importantly, it made them content delivery easier. They became able to run the class even during the lockdown period. Another important opportunity was that OE was very much fruitful for the students who could not attend the face to face class. The informant C4 wrote, *"OE has encourage teachers and students to use it as alternative means of teaching learning process"*. Likewise informant C1 expressed, *"The advantages we get depends. The more*

we are equipped with the tools, and trained with skills, the more advantages and opportunities of online education could be received”.

OE provided advantages to both the teachers and students in collecting learning resources, and creating learning environment, collaborative learning, teacher-students interaction and motivation. OE was a new practice to many of the HEIs. C6 opined, *“Online education in our institution is in beginning phase, though, the teachers and students are excited to continue it to run. It shows online education has played vital role in our institution”*. Likewise, C5 shared:

We realized its need and tried to introduce and implement among teachers and students. Nearly 90% teachers are familiar with it because of school's efforts conducting ICT training itself with the program of one teacher one lap top as well as encouraging teachers to participate on line training conducting by STFT, Nepal.

Some of the informants did not find satisfactory impression of OE. It was mainly because of poor management of online infrastructures. C7 shared, *“OE has not been the main way of content delivery due to the lack of needed infrastructures, skills”*. C2 opined, *“We run online education only in the special time when we feel it needed due to the lack of required infrastructure management”*.

Most of the student-informants responded that the opportunities of OE were conditional. The opportunities the students could take depend upon the availability of infrastructures and skills they gained. However the students who were completely unable to take face to face class, were able to take several benefits from OE. At least they could make interactions with the teacher and their friends about their queries. S5 reacted, *“While doing my self-study I couldn't be clear and confident about the problem related to the lesson. OE has provided me a platform that I can communicate and discuss with my teachers and friends”*. All the students were able to have many learning resources. In face to face mode, students were limited to have certain and limited resources. On the other hand, OE had made them to have a collection of several resources in very little cost. S3 said, *“Internet helped me to find many of the learning resources. Even if I don't find myself, my friends help me by sharing the learning resources”*. The students were also benefited

with the opportunities of frequent and easier interaction with their friends. Student S7 shared “*OE has saved my time. I needed to invest more than hour to get into touch with my friends but in OE, we have been able to contact with each other within a minute to discuss about the problems*”.

The excerpts in the paragraph above show that the chiefs of the campuses, and many of their teachers were able to take some advantages of OE. They found OE useful for resource collection and content delivery. The graphics, motions, and audio visual contents were the things that attracted the motivation of the students. Most importantly, they could store all the audio visual contents which could be useful for another time use; and for the students who are absent in the classroom. Moreover, correction, addition, and revision of their prepared lessons was very easy for the teachers.

Another important opportunity that OE provided was the extent of interaction and discussion among the students and between the teachers and students. The tools such as Facebook, Email, Skype, and Messenger were very useful for making interaction and discussion more frequent. Likewise, the tools such as Facebook group, Blogs, Google docs were useful for conduction collaborative activities. Similarly, the students were benefited with OE that though they were not able to attend the real-time classroom, they were able to listen and watch the slides and the document related to the lesson. Likewise, they were benefited to share the resources and to interact with their friend and teachers. All these opportunities were created by OE.

4.4 Problems and Challenges of Online Education

All the HEIs were in the beginning phase of online education. In some of them, it was due to the pandemic of corona and lockdown in the country, that they were compelled to run online mode of education. Therefore, there were several problems and challenges of OE in the HEIs in Dhankuta. C6 shared:

Online education in government institutions is not easier job. This is because the government itself has followed the traditional education system and has spent large amount yearly to fulfill fruitless education goal. In this condition, any government institution to attempt to run such a great program is not a joke. Too much

expenditure for computers' purchase, training for teachers and high speed of internet management was the great challenge for our institution.

C7 opined that the problems were both policy and practice related, and those were both at government level and local level. S/he wrote:

We were not fully determined to run online education mode of teaching and learning in the time of the students' admission. Therefore, our students and parents were not mentally prepared for the management of online education system. The mentality of the traditional methods of the teachers, and lack of their updates to online education and new methods, poverty in the society, and parents' inability to buy online education tools to their children, lack of budget to maintain adequate online infrastructures in the HEIs are some of the main difficulties to us.

Likewise, C2 stressed that problems are due to managerial problem of the infrastructures in the institutions, and due to poverty of the guardians. S/he opined:

The problems are that many of our students do not have access to online education tools, we have very low internet capacity, we do not have ICT lab and that we have inadequate desktops and laptops. It is also that many of our teachers and students do not have online education skills and updates.

C5 provided a list of the problems and challenges that s/he experienced while conducting OE. S/he pointed out:

The problems and challenges are: a) In total, 10% teachers have no laptop and they lack its knowledge, b) Most of the teachers are just learners of OE so they are not expert on it, c) No specific computer teacher managed by the government, d) Just 15 to 20 % teachers are capable themselves on online education and remain are learners, e) Lack of well managed computer lab with enough computers, f) No skilled manpower to handle computer lab, g) No access to internet, computer, smart phone to most of the students due to poverty that hinders on line education, h) Lack of interest as well as activeness of teachers to be updated on ICT.

The students shared that lack of internet and online learning tools such as laptop, smartphones, and internet were the main problems to the students. One of the students, S7 reacted, *“Internet is not available in our locality and I need to use my mobile data. It takes longer time for me to open the page”*. Another student, S1 shared, *“I need to use short smart phone to connect to the internet and the internet is very slow. It doesn’t have many other function of laptop, which is easier for me to use for my preparation and presentation”*. Likewise, lack of needed online skill was another problem for the students. It was first experience to many of the students using MS Teams and Zoom. They didn’t have necessary skills to prepare the documents for presentation.

The excerpts in the paragraph above illustrate that there were many problems and challenges of OE. Most importantly, poor ICT infrastructures that are the basic foundation of OE were the main challenges of online education. The HEIs were facing the problems such as low capacity internet, lack of ICT lab, inadequate number of laptops and desktops, lack of smartboards, lack of regular electricity, and lack of projectors; and poor physical features of classroom were some of the main challenges of OE to the HEIs. These affected their students too. Likewise some of the teachers didn’t have pedagogical and technological knowledge to conduct OE classes. They had not got any training related to the pedagogical skills required of OE.

The students were suffered from both poverty (i., e., financial problem to manage online education tools) and online education skills. They didn’t have electricity, laptops, and smart phones. Sometimes, a group of four/five students needed to share a single laptop due to the financial problems to purchase the online tools. Likewise they didn’t have basic online skills such as typing, preparing documents, preparing slides, sharing the learning researches, creating the Blogs, email etc. It was also that their parents were not aware of the importance of OE. All these were the some of the main problems and challenges of online education.

4.5 Possible Measures for the Improvement of Online Education

The online education was one of the mode of teaching and learning in most of the HEIs in Dhankuta. Therefore, the chiefs of HEIs had some experiences of running

educational programmes in online mode, and some knowledge of the opportunities and challenges of OE in the educational institutions. They also had some ideas about the possible ways for the improvement of online education. C6 shared:

Some of the possible measures for making improvement in current practice of OE are: (i) Firstly, everyone should think that the online education is today's need for any institution. (ii)The government should avoid the traditional education system and prioritize to online education system. (iii)The government should invest on management of the existing status of pre-requisites (especially, Internet connectivity; Internet capacity; computer lab; number of computer; teachers' training and students' access to online education tools in online education. (iv) The people should be awarded about the importance of online education, and (v) The planners should be encouraged to take this job ahead successfully.

Likewise, the internet provider company and the government can contribute more for the improvement of the online infrastructures. C4 expressed:

Some important ways for the improvement can be: (a) Internet provider companies should minimize the cost to be assessable to all the students. (b)There should be regular power supply. (c)The government should make the provision of making online education compulsory (include in the course). (d)The policy of online examination system should be made, and (e) Teaching learning based training should be conducted.

Some of the campus chiefs emphasized on the role of governmental policy for the improvement of online education. C7 wrote:

Online education should not be only a mode of teaching and learning, but the government should make a policy to get students for online education. There should not be dual policy of both online teaching and face to face teaching. This compels all the stakeholders to be determined to online education. Likewise, the government should manage frequent teacher refreshing and updating training programmes.

Likewise, C2 viewed, “All the students should have access to Internet, and other tools for online education, load shedding and power cut off should be completely avoided,

teachers should be trained, and the government should increase the investment to online education”. Likewise, C5 opined that the management of skilled man power, training, and subsidy for the students to manage online education tools. S/he stressed:

For better improvement, we need to consider on: a) Managing expert manpower in every education institution, b) Training to all teachers, c) Managing well equipped ICT lab, d) Reinforcing and encouraging students on online education, and e) Provision of promotion for teachers and incentive for the students, and implementation of online education provision making it compulsory by the government.

The students opined that there were many benefits of OE, but it had many challenges to face. To make better improvement in OE, they demanded internet facility and stronger infrastructure management in their institutions. S5 expressed, *“Internet facility should be made available everywhere. At least there must establish internet center (IC). At every locality, and the students need to be allowed to use internet without any cost. Likewise, S9 said, “The infrastructure of OE is not strong in our institution in such a way that we all students can use to OE tools. The size of ICT lab, number of the computers and the capacity of the internet must be strengthened”.*

Most of the chiefs of the HEIs suggested management of budget and the need of the formation of better government policy. They viewed that it is mainly the responsibility of the government to improve the quality of education. OE certainly plays important role in improving educational quality because it makes the students all time learners, it makes them resourceful and that it increases interaction discussion and collaboration between and among the teachers and students. The budget that the government allocated to education is too little for bringing educational improvement including OE. Therefore, the government need to increase the amount of the budget for the sector of education.. It is also that the government should make a far-sighted plans and policies to make improvement in OE. Likewise, parents-awareness programs, subsidy to students in remote area, and teacher training and refreshment training need to organize more frequently.

CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This last chapter deals with the main summary and the conclusion of the mini research. It also includes the implications of the study, and the future research as the guidelines for future researchers.

5.1 Summary

This study on online education in higher education institutions in Dhankuta district is an attempt to explore mainly the existing infrastructures and opportunities and problems of online education in the HEIs in Dhankuta district. The study also explore the status of existing infrastructures, and some of the ideas for making improvement in the existing situation of online education.

This study was guided by constructivist research paradigm, and it was based on qualitative research approach. The study made collection of the experiences of the chiefs/heads of HEIs as qualitative information using interview methods. Similarly, the experience of the students studying in HEIs were collected by means of FGD. Thematic analysis was used for the analysis and interpretation of the information collected.

It was found on the study that we had provided several benefits to the teachers and students. Most importantly we had made them more resourceful of learning materials and that there were more frequent interaction and collaborative works. However, OE was not effective because of the lack of basic infrastructure required. Particularly internet connectivity, internet speed, electricity, regular power supply, ICT lab, numbers of computers and projectors were quite inadequate in most of the institutions. Likewise, only a few of the teachers had technological knowledge to run OE smoothly. Neither the teachers had excess to adequate equipment nor had they got any training to run OE. Similarly, many other students had no access to online education tools such as internet, laptop and smartphones. Therefore, in spite of the teachers' and students' excitement towards OE, it couldn't have been effective for making improvement in the quality of education.

5.2 Conclusion

Information communication and information technology have been indispensable in the society of this 21st century. Though Nepal has not been able to make satisfactory progress of information and communication technology, the government has given more priority in its development in recent years. More particularly, as keeping physical distance was compulsory, and face to face classroom were closed due to lock down caused by Corona virus pandemic, many of the educational institutions have practiced online education using information and communication technologies. With reference to this context, this study has made an attempt to study online education related status, activities; and experiences of the chief/heads of the campuses and of the students in the HEIs in Dhankuta district.

The study concluded that the chiefs/heads, and most of the teachers in all the HEIs were positive towards online education. The students on the other hand, had mixed opinions about their impression towards OE. In general, though most of the HIEs in Dhankuta district are struggling to manage the basic infrastructures of online education, online education has created opportunities for the teachers and the students for having lots of learning resources and sharing ideas and materials. It has also helped them to make interaction, discussion more frequent, and to work in collaboration. However, some of the HEIs were unable to run online education due to the difficulties in infrastructure management, and inadequate online education skills. Even in the HEIs which conducted online education, many of the students (almost two third of the students) were unable to participate as they did not have access to online educational tools and skills of online education. Infrastructure development, training to the teachers of online education, and access to online education tools were the common challenges of all the HEIs in Dhankuta. The concerned authority need to consider these factors to make improvement in the existing situation of online education.

5.3 Implications

The opportunities and advantages of online education largely depends upon the context in which it is used. ICTs are the basic requisites of online education and the

productive use of ICTs increase the productivity of online education. The more the prerequisites of online education is strong, the more benefits of could be achieved. Though having stakeholders' positive attitude towards online education, some of the HEIs in Dhankuta district have not been able to conduct online education due to the challenges such as infrastructure development, training to the teachers, and the students' access to ICT tools. To have better advantages of OE these challenges needed to be addressed by the concerned authority.

This study has made an attempt to study the current status of the infrastructures that online education requires, and also to analyze the opportunities and challenges of online education to the HEIs located in Dhankuta district. Some of the implications of this study have been pointed out below:

The chiefs/heads of the HEIs may find this study significant to understand the opportunities and challenges of online education in the other HEIs in the district. They can also have ideas about the measures for the improvement of online education. Likewise, the teachers and the students also can have ideas of the difficulties and benefits of online education and make further plans and strategies to select their methods and materials.

The findings of this study can also be useful for the government, NGOs and INGOs, and other concerned authorities to make plans or revise theirs plans and strategies related to online education. Similarly all the researchers, scholars and other individuals who are interested in online education may take benefits from this study report to enrich their understanding of online education.

5.4 Further Research

This research entitled opportunities and challenges of OE in the HEIs in Dhankuta district made an effort to explore mainly the existing infrastructures and opportunities and challenges of OE in the HEIs in Dhankuta district. The study was purely qualitative, using mail questionnaire and FGD as the research methods. Due to corona pandemic and country lockdown, face to face interview with the informants was impossible. A further research including both qualitative and quantitative information using the methods like observation

and face to face interview could be carried out for more in depth and comprehensive study of OE.

Project Fund

The fund of this research project was partly supported by the Research Management Cell Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta.

Notes on the Contributor

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APPENDICES

Appendix-A: Mail questionnaire

तलका प्रश्नहरूको संक्षिप्त उत्तर दिनुहुन अनुरोध छ (नेपाली वा अंग्रेजी कुनै एक भाषामा)। Please give your answer the following questions in brief (Either in English or in Nepali language)

१) यहाँको संस्थामा कति समयदेखि अनलाइन शिक्षा (Online Education) परिचित र संचालित छ ? (For how long has online education been introduced/conducted in your institution?)

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२) अनलाइन शिक्षाप्रति यहाँको कस्तो धारणा छ ? (What is your general impression about online education?)

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३) अनलाइन शिक्षाप्रति यहाँको संस्थाका शिक्षकहरूको, र विद्यार्थीहरूको धारणा समग्रमा कस्तो पाउनु भएको छ ? (What is the teachers', and students' general attitude towards online education in your institution?)

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४) यहाँको संस्थामा अनलाइन शिक्षाको कस्तो भूमिका छ? (What is the role of online education in your institution?)

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५) यहाँको संस्थामा अनलाइन शिक्षाको लागि आवश्यक पूर्वाधारहरू (खासगरी इन्टरनेट जडान, इन्टरनेट क्षमता, कम्प्युटर ल्याब, कम्प्युटरको संख्या, शिक्षकमा अनलाइन शिक्षाको सिप र तालिम, विद्यार्थीमा अनलाइन शिक्षाका साधनको पहुँच र सिप) को वर्तमान अवस्था कस्तो छ ? (What is the existing status of pre-requisites

(especially, Internet connectivity; Internet capacity; computer lab; number of computer; teachers' skills of online education, and training; students' access to online education tools, and their skills) of online education in your institution?)

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६) यहाँको संस्थामा अनलाइन शिक्षाले शिक्षक तथा विद्यार्थीमा के कस्ता अवसरहरु सिर्जना गरेको छ ? (What types of opportunities has the online education created in your institution?)

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७) यहाँको संस्थामा अनलाइन शिक्षा सम्बन्धी (जस्तै अनलाइन शिक्षाको भौतिक पूर्वाधार, शिक्षक तथा विद्यार्थीमा अनलाइन शिक्षाका साधनको पहुँच ,अनलाइन शिक्षाका सिप र तालिम, प्रशासनिक व्यवस्थापन, र अन्य) के कस्ता समस्या तथा चुनौतिहरु छन् ? (What types of problems/challenges (e. g, infrastructures of online education; teachers' and students' access to online education tools; skills and training of online education; administrative management; and others) related to online education does your institution have?)

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८) यहाँको संस्थामा अनलाइन शिक्षाको सम्भाव्यता कस्तो छ ? (What is the future possibility of online education in your institution?)

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९) अनलाइन शिक्षाको सुधारका लागि के कस्ता उपायहरु हुन सक्छन् ? (What can be possible measures for the improvement of online education?)

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The End

Appendix-B: FGD questionnaire

- How long have you been involved in online education?
- What is your general impression of online education?
- What is the role of online education in the education system?
- What is your access to ICT tools?
- What are the opportunities of online education in your experience?
- What are the difficulties and challenges for you while being involved in online education? (infrastructure related, technological skill related, teacher related, syllabus related, administration related)
- What are the possibilities of online education?
- What can be the measures for bringing improvement in existing situation of OE?
- What do you expect form your institution and the government?

Appendix-C: List of the Higher Educational Institutions (Campuses)

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-----------------------|
| a) Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta | TU constituent campus |
| b) Gokundeshwar Campus, Dhankuta | TU affiliated campus |
| c) Bhasha Campus, Kagate | TU affiliated campus |
| d) Hile Campus, Hile | TU affiliated campus |
| e) Jalapa Devi Campus, Pakhribas | TU affiliated campus |
| f) Jeetpur Campus, Jeetpur | TU affiliated campus |
| g) Budhuk Campus, Budhuk | TU affiliated campus |